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D7.3 – Joint Exploitation Plan

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDIs	Blue Data Infrastructures
CCP	Cloud Container Platform
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	Italian National Research Council
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
D4Science Infrastructure	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
DIVAnd	Data interpolating variational analysis in n dimensions
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMB	European Marine Board
EM	Exploitation Measure
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EO	Exploitation Objective
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EU HFR	European High Frequency Radar Node
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
HF	High-Frequency
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MEI	Marine Environmental Indicators

MPA	Marine Protected Area
NRT	Near-Real-Time
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSI	Enhanced Storm Severity
TBD	To Be Defined
TRIX	Trophic State Index
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WB	Workbench
WP	Working Package

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document delivers the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Joint Exploitation Plan**. It outlines the exploitation strategy, objectives and measures that will be deployed to support the long-term exploitation of the results stemming from the **HE Blue-Cloud 2026 project**, jointly by Consortium Partners. The Plan focuses on the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud 2026 services and assets as a synergetic digital ecosystem, encompassing and connecting identified Key Exploitable Results, namely:

- Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment.
- Blue-Cloud 2026 Core and Generic Services.
- Blue-Cloud 2026 Spatial & Data Management Services.
- Blue-Cloud 2026 High Value Thematic Services.
- Blue-Cloud 2026 Training Courses & Materials.
- Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030.

The Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium has identified a **strategic pathway** for long-term exploitation of its open science ecosystem as a **marine thematic node** within the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** (see section 2). In this framework, Blue-Cloud’s built know-how and results will be harnessed to bridge [EDITO](#) -the public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean- to EOSC, contributing to support major EU marine data services -such as EMODnet and Copernicus Marine- and related EDITO knowledge assets in driving data provision into EOSC. The output knowledge and assets generated in Blue-Cloud, including its underpinning infrastructure, will be used to contribute to consolidate a marine thematic node in EOSC, establishing the conditions that can guide the transition towards becoming a core component of the EDITO program, for long-term sustainability. Within this overall framework, the following **Exploitation Objectives** (EO) are envisioned (see section 3), across key assets (described in section 4) and a range of key target users (described in section 5):

- EO1: Institutional integration in the EOSC Federation.
- EO2: Uptake of existing core, generic and thematic services by users working in the marine and aquatic domains.
- EO3: Uptake of existing core and generic services by other EOSC nodes, supporting the development of the EOSC Federation.
- EO4: Marine knowledge landscape alignment and added value contribution.
- EO5: Community engagement, capacity building & representation.

To achieve these objectives, a number of exploitation measures have been defined, and resources required for execution have been either committed or identified (Section 6), towards long-term, sustained impact beyond the project lifetime. Exploitation targets have been established (Section 7). The delivery of a marine thematic node will contribute to shortening the research-to-innovation cycle, enabling its users to harness artificial intelligence (AI) to catalyse the transformation of marine data to products, and foster cross-discipline collaboration. In the long term, it will contribute to enhancing existing marine knowledge, science-to-policy interfaces, and to informing science-based ocean management and governance in support of Mission “Restore Our Ocean & Waters” and related EU policies and strategies.

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1 Objective and scope of this document

This document delivers the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Joint Exploitation Plan**. It outlines the exploitation strategy, objectives and measures that will be deployed to support the long-term exploitation of the results stemming from the HE “**Blue-Cloud 2026**” project, jointly by Consortium Partners. The Plan focuses on the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud 2026 services and assets as a synergetic digital ecosystem, encompassing and connecting identified Key Exploitable Results.

The Blue-Cloud 2026 Joint Exploitation Plan does not address the exploitation of stand-alone results by individual partners. While such project results will be capitalised by Consortium Partners to further evolve their respective organisational missions, thus adding to the long-term impact of the project from a research and innovation perspective, the Plan rather seeks to guide the synergetic exploitation of key results by selected target audiences, towards maximising the project value for the marine research and wider scientific communities, and enhancing the marine knowledge value chain. Aspects pertaining to the sustainability of the project results and thus impacting the viability of this Exploitation Plan are not part of the scope of this document, as they are specifically addressed in the project deliverable D7.5 “Blue-Cloud 2026 Sustainability & Strategy Plan”.

2 Exploitation vision

The Horizon Europe “Blue-Cloud 2026” project has built on the outcomes of the Horizon 2020 “Blue-Cloud pilot” project to further evolve an open science ecosystem that enables researchers, data scientists and software developers to build analytical tools and services that accelerate the generation of marine knowledge. This ecosystem is underpinned by a Virtual Research Environment offering state-of-the-art services, applications and cloud resources that its users can leverage to build, evolve and share their solutions.

Both the Horizon 2020 “Blue-Cloud pilot” (2019-2023) and Horizon Europe “Blue-Cloud 2026” (2023-2026) projects were foreseen as testing grounds for advancing open science in the marine domain and as precursors of the European Digital Twin Ocean. The Blue-Cloud Vision 2030¹ aligned with this purpose and guided Blue-Cloud 2026 project developments in its initial years. However, the landscape in which the Blue-Cloud 2026 project operates has changed considerably since the development of its Vision 2030. Significant developments have been the further evolution of the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** on one hand, and on the other, the launch of the **European Digital Twin Ocean** and the deployment of **EDITO** (<https://www.edito.eu>), its underpinning public infrastructure, powered by **EMODnet** and **Copernicus Marine Service**, which supports large-scale scientific collaboration, near-real-time processing, and

¹ Vera, J., Larkin, K., Delaney, C., Tonné, N., Cisternino, S., Calewaert, J.-B., Pittonet, S., Drago, F., Schaap, D. M. A., Pagano, P., Obaton, D., Ellenbroek, A., Cabrera, P., & Drudi, M. (2022). *Blue-Cloud D6.4 Strategic Roadmap (Release 2) (Versión 1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10067460>

seamless integration across cloud, HPC, and marine data ecosystems. **EDITO** is intended to evolve into a long-term, sustained European infrastructure.

Following consultations amongst the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium and with the wider marine research and innovation community during 2024-2025 to adapt and positively contribute to these developments, the Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium has identified a **strategic pathway** for long-term exploitation of its open science ecosystem as a **marine and aquatic thematic node** within **EOSC** (namely, as the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin of the Ocean”). This pathway has led to revisiting the Blue-Cloud Vision 2030, reflecting on the opportunity of adapting and contributing to these developments:

Blue-Cloud Vision 2030

To consolidate a marine thematic node in EOSC, establishing the technical and governance conditions that will guide the transition towards becoming a core component of the EDITO core infrastructure platform of the European Digital Twin Ocean.

The EOSC Node | Digital Twin of the Ocean will champion a vision where major EU marine knowledge assets (i.e. EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, EDITO), and environmental and marine Research Infrastructures (from ESFRI and beyond) are central to driving marine data provision in EOSC, supporting and catalysing open science developments in the marine and freshwater domains.

In this framework, Blue-Cloud 2026’s built know-how and results will be harnessed to bridge EDITO to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), contributing to support major EU marine data services, i.e., EMODnet and Copernicus Marine- and related EDITO knowledge assets in driving data provision into EOSC. These efforts will further continue to stress the importance of EC operational services for *in situ* and satellite marine data sharing and promote data ingestion from a large number of sources and Research Infrastructures into EMODnet, Copernicus Marine and/or EDITO, for the benefit of the wider EOSC community and into the European Digital Twin Ocean.

The output knowledge and results of the project will thus contribute to enhance the EOSC contribution to EDITO, for the benefit of marine and wider research communities, as well as to support the long-term exploitation and sustainability of the project legacy. Such an exploitation pathway will allow the delivery of the Blue-Cloud Vision 2030, within the knowledge ecosystem powered by EDITO.

3 Exploitation objectives

The output knowledge and assets generated in Blue-Cloud 2026, including its underpinning infrastructure, will be used to contribute to consolidate a marine thematic node in EOSC, establishing the conditions that can guide the transition towards becoming a core component of the EDITO program, for long-term sustainability. The activities will be carried out in accordance with, and aligned to, the strategic and technical guidance provided by the Blue Cloud 2026 “Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) Task Force”. Within this overall framework, the following **Exploitation Objectives** (EO) are envisioned:

1. EO1: Integration in the EOSC Federation as a node:

- To integrate into the EOSC Federation as an official thematic node dedicated to marine and aquatic data (“EOSC Node Digital Twin of the Ocean”), which will both expose EDITO resources and embed the core services (VRE, DD&AS) and assets (VLabs, Workbenches) evolved during the Blue-Cloud pilot and Blue-Cloud 2026 projects into the core EOSC infrastructure, towards enhancing their visibility, interoperability, and user reach, and ensuring that all resources are discoverable, accessible, and interoperable according to EOSC Federation policies.

Impact: Sustainable exploitation of core services and assets beyond the project lifetime.

2. EO2: Uptake of existing core, generic and thematic services by users working in the marine and aquatic domains:

- To facilitate and promote the exploitation of existing core services (VRE) by research and innovation projects working in the marine and aquatic domains, e.g., Horizon Europe funded projects (B2B).
- To facilitate and promote the exploitation of existing thematic services (Virtual Labs, Workbenches) by users actively involved in marine and aquatic related research, e.g., marine researchers, innovators, Research Infrastructures who can benefit from operating in the EOSC environment (B2C).

Impact: Shorten the research-to-innovation cycle, enabling users to harness artificial intelligence (AI) to improve the transformation of marine data to products.

3. EO3: Uptake of existing core and generic services by other EOSC nodes, supporting the development of the EOSC Federation:

- To expose core and generic services developed in the framework of the Blue-Cloud pilot and Blue-Cloud 2026 projects to other EOSC nodes within the EOSC Federation, so they can harness them to build thematic services for other domains.

Impact: Enable cross-domain, multidisciplinary science

4. EO4: Landscape alignment and added value contribution:

- To harness the Blue-Cloud 2026 project’s knowledge outputs and related services to enable the flow of new marine data currently not covered nor targeted by existing, core EU services into EDITO, including when possible via EMODnet and/or Copernicus Marine Service, avoiding overlapping or duplication of such services.
- To harness the project’s knowledge outputs and related services to federate and harness other (non-marine) data (e.g., wider environmental data, life sciences data, socio economic data) by improving their FAIRness and functionality for discovery, access, and machine-actionability via the EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean and in-flow into EDITO, for the benefit of the marine research, science and digital twinning communities.

Impact: Enhance existing marine knowledge, science-to-policy interfaces to enable science-based ocean management and governance in support of Mission “Restore Our Ocean & Waters” and related EU policies and strategies.

5. **EO5: Community Engagement, Capacity Building & Representation:**

- To deliver training to researchers, students and early career ocean scientists on data literacy and use of e-infrastructures to promote FAIR and CARE data principles, grow the community in EOSC, and to voice the community needs before EOSC Governance.

Impact: Expand the user base, build skills, and ensure uptake by next-generation of ocean professionals

4 Target users

Blue-Cloud 2026 identifies **researchers** - more specifically *marine scientists, data scientists & modellers, software developers* and *computer scientists* - as the **primary users** of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) emerging from the project (see Section 5). Beyond these users, there are other **secondary** and **tertiary** users in the project’s landscape that can benefit from its services and offer relevant pathways for exploitation and are thus also targeted for this purpose.

Blue-Cloud Target User Segments

Figure 1: Blue-Cloud 2026 Target User Segments

The Target Users identified for exploitation are outlined in Table 1:

Table 1: Target Users for Exploitation

TG#	Type	Stakeholders concerned
TG1	Primary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine researchers • Data scientists & environmental modelers • Computer scientists • Software developers
TG2	Secondary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMODnet, Copernicus, EDITO • Other EOSC nodes
TG3	Tertiary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC & international policy bodies • EOSC and national (EOSC related) funding agencies

5 Key assets for exploitation

Given the Exploitation Objectives laid out in Section 3, the following KERs of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project have been identified for exploitation in this Joint Exploitation Plan (see Table 1):

Table 2: Blue-Cloud 2026 Key Exploitable Results

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Owner
KER 1	Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment built on D4Science.	CNR-ISTI
KER 2	Blue-Cloud 2026 Core and Generic services offered by D4Science to support VRE users, as well as the set up of other thematic nodes, including for cross-node collaboration.	CNR-ISTI
KER 3	Blue-Cloud 2026 Spatial & Data Management Services available to improve the offering of FAIR marine data services to EOSC users.	MARIS, ULiege, BODC, AWI, VLIZ, Ifremer, Research Infrastructures (i.e., EuroArgo, ELIXIR ENA, MGnify, EMSO, EMBRC, ICOS, SIOS, SeaDataNet, EuroOBIS, and EcoTaxa)

KER 4	Blue-Cloud 2026 High-Value Thematic Services (Virtual Labs & Workbenches), offered as FAIR marine thematic services to EOSC users.	CMCC, CNR, EMBL, ETHZ, FORTH, HCMR, IEEE, Ifremer, IH, INGV, IRD, KNMI, Oceanscope, OGS, Pokapok, SMHI, SOCIB, SU, ULiege, VLIZ
KER 5	Blue-Cloud 2026 Training courses & materials	IH, SOCIB, IEEE, ULiège, VLIZ, CMCC, OGS, INGV, KNMI, CNR, IRD, FORTH, FAO, OTGA, ETT, EuroGOOS
KER 6	Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030	SSBE, CNR, Trust-IT, MARIS, Ifremer, VLIZ, EGI

Each of these KERs are further described in the following sub-sections.

4.1 Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a digital environment that provides computing platforms and analytical services to facilitate the collaboration between researchers. The Blue-Cloud VRE is powered by the D4Science infrastructure. The infrastructure exploits cloud-based hardware resources (hardware layer) through the exploitation of a service layer organised in four software frameworks. The hardware layer is organized as a dynamic pool of virtual machines, supporting computation and storage. It consists of an OpenStack installation, supporting the deployment of services in the upper layer by provision of computational and storage resources. The services layer is organized into e-infrastructure middleware, storage, and end-user services. The VRE components range from services to promote the collaboration among its users, to services supporting the execution of analytical tasks embedded in a distributed computing infrastructure, to services enabling the co-creation of entire Virtual Laboratories (VLabs).

More in-depth descriptions of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment and its common facilities are available here:

- Blue-Cloud 2026 - D5.1 Blue Cloud VRE Common Services 1st Release: <https://zenodo.org/records/10512783>
 - Blue-Cloud 2026 - D5.3 Blue Cloud VRE federated infrastructures 1st release: <https://zenodo.org/records/14751038>
- Blue-Cloud 2026 - D5.2 VRE Operation Report: <https://zenodo.org/records/12667549>

4.2 Blue-Cloud 2026 Core and Generic Services

Blue-Cloud 2026 has evolved a robust set of core (EOSC related) services, which are listed in Table 2 below. These services ensure compliance with EOSC requirements, providing the essential technical capabilities

for a trusted and secure federated system in the entire research data lifecycle, from discovery and access to analysis and publication.

Table 3: Blue-Cloud Core Services

EOSC EU Node Offer	Specific (Blue-Cloud 2026) service offer to be exploited under a potential EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”
<p>Resource Catalogue and Registry Services: <i>Catalogue of resources that can be accessed through the EOSC Node with a search engine to discover, access and order them</i></p>	<p>The Blue-Cloud 2026 catalogue operates as a central, unified repository for scientific products, services, and data. By employing standardized metadata formats and protocols, the catalogue not only provides a powerful tool for resource discovery but also acts as a crucial interoperability layer. Users are empowered to publish their methodologies, workflows, and code, transforming the repository from a simple catalogue into a dynamic hub for collaboration and multidisciplinary analysis.</p>
<p>Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI): <i>AI (AARC Blueprint-compliant) enabling access via federated credentials</i></p>	<p>Advanced AAI, including OpenID Connect (OIDC) and User Managed Authorization (UMA 2), to provide a secure and granular access control system. This infrastructure is a cornerstone of the trusted federated system, allowing for the definition and enforcement of fine-grained access policies. Single sign-on capabilities provide a seamless and secure user experience in the federation.</p>
<p>Helpdesk: <i>Support incident response and requests for services and resources</i></p>	<p>A dedicated Helpdesk staffed by specialists with expertise in both technical infrastructure and marine and aquatic science, offering comprehensive user documentation, FAQs, and links to training programs and best practice guidelines</p>
<p>Service Monitoring <i>Monitor the availability and quality of the Node services</i></p>	<p>A comprehensive service monitoring with integrated dashboard, where authorised users can access real-time status updates on all services and resources., i.e.tracking uptime, response times, and resource utilization.</p>
<p>Service and Research Product Accounting <i>Track and record usage of resources</i></p>	<p>A secure and GDPR compliant environment for managing accounting data related to service usage and product generation. Accessible through both the VRE and specific Virtual Laboratories to support reporting, analytics, and auditing.</p>
<p>Order Management <i>A framework and interface to request access to resources</i></p>	<p>A streamlined interface for researchers to place an order for the creation of a new Virtual Laboratory by defining requirements, including the necessary tools, applications, and computational resources, through a structured request process.</p>

<p>Configuration Management System: <i>Shared internal space to store information on Node capabilities and on how services are provided</i></p>	<p>This service provides users with the flexibility to customize their existing V Labs. Researchers can select and configure the specific tools and applications they need, leveraging the D4Science infrastructure for computational and storage resources. This approach ensures that researchers have the tailored resources required to conduct their work efficiently, from collaborative data sharing to complex analysis.</p>
<p>User Space (Gateway): <i>Dynamic customisable dashboard, where the node user logs-in, offering easy access to the Node resources.</i></p>	<p>The gateway serves as the centralised entry point for all users, providing seamless access to a wide range of tools and resources. This platform integrates multiple data sources and computational tools, fostering a cohesive and intuitive user experience that is essential for promoting broad adoption and community engagement.</p>
<p>Application Workflow Management: <i>Orchestrate services, datasets and research objects</i></p>	<p>The Node offers powerful capabilities for creating and executing analytical workflows. Through V Labs within a VRE, researchers are able to design, test, and evaluate innovative computational flows, ensuring a streamlined path from hypothesis to result.</p>

Beyond the core services, the Blue-Cloud 2026’s VRE offers a suite of **generic services** designed to enhance the overall user experience, ensure service quality, and foster community support. These services are detailed below.

Interactive Computing and Collaborative Platforms

- **File Sync & Share (Workspace):** Provides researchers with a secure, centralized location for storing data and resources. This service ensures data integrity and high availability through automatic replication across multiple storage devices. It also supports file versioning, history management, and metadata management, ensuring all data is well-documented and easily accessible. A key feature is the seamless connectivity with analytical tools like JupyterLab, RStudio, and the Collaborative Computing Platform (CCP), which streamlines data analysis workflows.
- **RStudio & JupyterLab:** These services provide integrated development environments for data analysis, statistical computing, and interactive computing. They enable users to work with notebooks, code, and data in a collaborative manner, supporting reproducible research. By supporting multiple programming languages (including R, Python, and Julia), these services are invaluable for data exploration, analysis, visualization, and the creation of shareable documents.
- **Galaxy:** As a web-based platform, Galaxy promotes accessible, reproducible, and transparent data analyses. It empowers users to perform complex computational analyses across various scientific domains through a user-friendly interface for running tools, managing data, and tracking analysis history.
- **CCP Services:** The Collaborative Computing Platform provides a comprehensive suite of tools to support collaborative research. These services include robust data manipulation, analysis, and

sharing capabilities, fostering efficient teamwork by providing shared workspaces and communication features.

The core and generic capabilities developed in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project are technical tools and services, installed and configured at the D4Science e-infrastructure. These tools and services can be exploited as underpinning services by the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” (i.e., offered to users of the node for developing, testing, deploying, and operating marine-focused applications, such as analytical workflows and data lakes), but they can also be offered to the EOSC Federation for use by other EOSC nodes and third parties. These secondary users can integrate such services in their own applications, which operate beyond the marine domain, but in related knowledge thematics, such as e.g., in the wider ESFRI environmental domain.

4.3 Blue-Cloud 2026 Spatial & Data Management Services

In addition to the generic services described in the previous section, the following generic services have been integrated in the Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE and can be exploited by marine scientists and researchers.

- **Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) Facilities:** This suite of tools is essential for managing and sharing geospatial data:
 - GeoNetwork facilitates the management of spatially referenced resources, offering powerful metadata editing and search functions.
 - GeoPortal supports the publication, access, and management of GIS projects, enabling users to visualize and analyze spatial data within a collaborative environment.
 - GeoServer allows users to publish and share geospatial data using open standards, making it a crucial tool for data dissemination.
 - THREDDS Data Server (TDS) provides metadata and data access for scientific datasets, supporting various remote data access protocols such as OPeNDAP and OGC WMS.
- **Data Management Facilities:** To accommodate diverse data types, the Node provides both NoSQL and Relational Database Management Systems. NoSQL databases are used to handle large volumes of unstructured and semi-structured data with flexible data models. In contrast, Relational databases manage and organize structured data efficiently, ensuring high data integrity and security.
- **Data Lake Annex and Subsetting Services:** A key challenge in marine research is managing and combining vast, diverse, and often unwieldy datasets. Blue-Cloud 2026 provides a suite of services (i.e., webODV, DIVAnd, Semantic Analyser, Beacon) that enable users to efficiently access, subset, and analyze data within data lakes, making large datasets more manageable and interoperable. This dramatically lowers the barrier to entry for researchers working with big data.

Table 4: Ad-hoc Data Lake and Sub-setting Services Offered in Blue-Cloud

Service	Description	Owner
webODV	webODV provides online Ocean Data View services like the extraction, analysis, exploration and visualization of oceanographic and other environmental data.	AWI
DIVAnd	DIVAnd (Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis, in n-dimensions) is a tool to interpolate observations on a regular grid using the variational inverse method.	ULiege
Semantic Analyser	Powerful semantic tool which automatically matches free text with controlled vocabulary terms and maps concepts across vocabularies, using a semantic artefact knowledge base to extract and identify semantic content from data and metadata files, thus facilitating metadata harmonization & data interoperability.	BODC
Beacon	Beacon is a data lake software that provides users with fast and easy access to subsets of data originating from large data collections, on the fly with high performance, and allows to extract specific data based on the user’s request. This software is designed to return one single harmonised file as output, regardless of whether the input contains different data types	MARIS

4.4 Blue-Cloud 2026 High Value Thematic Services

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project features two different types of “demonstrators”, namely “**Workbenches**” and “**Virtual Labs**”. These demonstrators not only serve as “use cases” for the core and generic services offered by Blue-Cloud 2026, but also represent high value thematic services that have been set up with specific objectives and target audiences. Jointly, they build up a catalogue of High Value Thematic Services that cater to the marine (data) science, research and innovation community (see Table 4).

Blue-Cloud 2026 High-Value Thematic Services (Virtual Labs & Workbenches) are composed of different, individually exploitable assets that have already been the subject of specific exploitation plans (i.e., the Blue-Cloud 2026 VLabs and Workbenches). For the purpose of this plan, these assets have been grouped together around common service categories, which cater to similar target audiences.

Table 5: Blue-Cloud 2026 Thematic Services

Service	Type	Description
Integration of Coastal observations along Europe	VLab	The Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE) Virtual Lab provides a platform for accessing, integrating, and analysing coastal ocean observations across Europe. It focuses on data collected by the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI) and other European Blue Data Infrastructures, facilitating the study of coastal processes such as biological connectivity, contaminant dispersion, and the effects of river outflows. The Virtual Lab offers tools for advanced data exploration, including statistical analyses, correlation assessments, and interactive visualisations. These capabilities support the examination of coastal impacts from major storms and the evaluation of repeated glider sections, enhancing the understanding of coastal dynamics.
Coastal Currents from Observations	VLab	The Coastal Currents from Observations Virtual Lab in Blue-Cloud 2026 enables users to generate integrated ocean surface current maps by merging data from multiple sources. It uses direct and indirect current measurements, including High Frequency (HF) radar, drifter observations, and geostrophic currents derived from satellite altimetry. The integration relies on the DIVAnd (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) method, which applies physical constraints such as coastline boundaries, horizontal divergence, and momentum balance to improve the reliability of the output. The main feature of the Virtual Lab is a customisable service delivered through Jupyter notebooks. Users can select a coastal region—depending on data availability and the extent of HF radar coverage, typically ranging from 50 to 200 km offshore—and produce gridded surface current maps in NetCDF format. These maps support Lagrangian simulations, allowing the visualisation of artificial drifter trajectories from user-defined release points. The output also serves as input for the MEDSLIK-II oil spill model, which will be deployed in a Docker container to simulate pollutant dispersion scenarios.
Carbon Plankton Dynamics	VLab	The Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Virtual Lab provides a modelling environment to simulate interactions between nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus in marine ecosystems. At its core is a Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus (NPZD) model that runs in carbon units, enabling consistent tracking of carbon flows through various ecosystem processes. Initially implemented and validated in the southern

		<p>North Sea, the model has since been applied to the northern Adriatic Sea. This allows users to explore phytoplankton dynamics in different marine settings and examine factors influencing biomass variability.</p> <p>The system uses environmental input data such as sea surface temperature, salinity, nutrient concentrations (including DIN, PO₄, and SiO₄), and carbon-related variables like atmospheric pCO₂, wind speed, and pH. These inputs inform the model's representation of primary and secondary productivity, organic matter degradation, and carbon exchanges with the atmosphere and rivers.</p>
Marine Environmental Indicators	VLab	<p>The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab allows users to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas and support the decision-making process for ocean management. Multiple data sources are exploited in a unique data analysis service, which will allow the online computation of indicators through either Jupyter Notebooks or a customised web application that exploits the VRE Analytics Engine services for computing the indicator's outputs. The produced indicator outputs can contribute to initiatives such as the Copernicus Marine Ocean State Report or Med-CORDEX. Through this VLab, users can implement available algorithms to produce indicators, such as the Ocean Heat Content (OHC), Marine Heat Wave (MHW), Trophic Index (TRIX) and the Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 (SSI V2).</p>
Global Fisheries Atlas	VLab	<p>The Global Fisheries Atlas VLab provides a hands-on learning experience to explore the use of the Global Tuna Atlas and GRSF catalogue for studying and managing fish populations. The VLab allows users to navigate and analyse the data provided by these tools, including creating maps and visualisations of tuna distribution and migration patterns. Overall, this VLab provides a comprehensive and interactive learning experience that contributes to enhancing global understanding of tuna biology and management.</p>
EOV Workbench for Physics – Temperature & Salinity	EOV Data Collection - Workbench	<p>The EOV Workbench for Physics has developed an analytical workflow that helps generate added value Temperature and Salinity datasets by integrating data coming from multiple marine data infrastructures. The workbench contributes to accelerate the production of data products along the marine data value chain, by rapidly deriving midstream data products and downstream information products.</p>
EOV Workbench for Eutrophication	EOV Data Collection	<p>Currently, several datasets in different data infrastructures with their own QC/QA have to be synchronised manually. This Workbench has defined and implemented an efficient production workflow to merge multi-source</p>

	ion - Workb ench	datasets managed by Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet Chemistry and the World Ocean Database, together with key EU Research Infrastructures (RI), to build highly qualified EOV datasets for eutrophication variables: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen.
EOV & EBV Workbench for Ecosystems	EOV Data Collect ion - Workb ench	The primary purpose of the Ecosystem Workbench is to improve the availability, quality, and interoperability of large collections of plankton distribution, biomass and biodiversity observations and extrapolated biogeographies. A habitat modelling workflow has been developed to generate high-quality interpolated maps of these plankton entities at the global scale, in order to produce ecosystem-level EOVs.

These High Value Thematic Services can be exploited by marine researchers and scientists to:

- Improve and accelerate the transformation of marine data to specific products.
- Inspire and accelerate community-driven innovation to address ocean challenges.
- Accelerate monitoring services to support environmental and ocean related policy objectives.

4.5 Blue-Cloud 2026 Training courses and materials

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has produced training courses and materials to support key Target Audiences (i.e., marine researchers) in the use and exploitation of its services. These courses have been produced in collaboration with the **OceanTeacher Global Academy (OTGA)**. Coordinated by UNESCO-IOC, OTGA provides the e-learning backbone for the **Blue-Cloud Training Academy** (<https://blue-cloud.org/training-academy>), with a view to secure their long-term exploitation beyond the project.

Through Blue-Cloud Training Academy and the OTGA platform, marine researchers can access self-paced courses, webinars, and blended training to build skills in FAIR data management, marine biodiversity monitoring, and the practical use of Blue-Cloud tools such as the Virtual Research Environment (VRE), Virtual Laboratories (VLabs), and Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) Workbenches. Selected OTGA courses are co-branded with Blue-Cloud 2026, guiding users to make the most of Blue-Cloud data, services, and analytical capabilities. These courses were designed by Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium members who are VLab experts. Table 5 provides an overview of the OTGA courses that are available now.

Table 6: Blue-Cloud Training Courses Offered at OTGA platform

Course	Value proposition	Access link
How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Coastal Ocean Currents from Observations.	Learn to integrate and analyse HF radar, drifter, and satellite data to produce surface current maps—key for drift modelling and coastal impact studies.	https://oceanexpert.org/event/4857

<p>How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Carbon Plankton Dynamics.</p>	<p>Explore how to link biological, chemical, and carbon datasets to investigate plankton productivity and ecosystem change in a user-friendly VLab environment.</p>	<p>https://oceanexpert.org/event/4858</p>
<p>Navigating the Global Fisheries Atlas Virtual Laboratory: Tools and Techniques.</p>	<p>Gain practical skills to access and visualise global fisheries data, supporting analyses for sustainable fisheries management and marine policy.</p>	<p>https://oceanexpert.org/event/4861</p>
<p>Mastering Coastal Ocean Observations with the Blue-Cloud VLab</p>	<p>To equip ocean scientists with the knowledge and skills to effectively navigate, utilize, understand and customize the Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe Virtual Lab for accessing, analyzing, and contributing to research on coastal ocean processes.</p>	<p>To be published in January2026</p>
<p>How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Marine Environmental Indicators</p>	<p>Learn to navigate and use a VLab within Blue-Cloud VRE to access and analyze marine data. Apply Jupyter Notebooks and Python to process datasets, compute environmental indicators, and visualize results. Develop skills to interpret key marine indicators such as TRIX, Marine Heatwaves, and Ocean Heat Content, exploring their spatial and temporal patterns to identify environmental trends and hotspots.</p>	<p>To be published in January 2026</p>

4.6 Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030

The **Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap to 2030** is a foresight planning document providing guidance and policy recommendations for the future evolution of the Blue-Cloud digital ecosystem, towards the

delivery of the Blue-Cloud Vision 2030. Initially developed over the course of the three-year “Blue-Cloud pilot” project, the Roadmap² is the result of a collective reflection of Blue-Cloud partners, experts and stakeholders on how the project results can be exploited and evolved into the future to maximise their impact, aligning with wider developments at European and global level and creating new opportunities for Ocean, science-based innovation in support of the European Union (EU) Green Deal and the United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030, and the EU Ocean Pact. In view of significant developments in the European marine knowledge landscape (as introduced in Section 2), the Roadmap is in the process of being updated, again through an interactive process of stakeholder consultations that concluded in December 2025 (see milestone 34 of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project). The resulting Roadmap will be available by June 2026 and it will be used to continue guiding the long-term evolution and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud 2026 results.

6 Linking Target users to Key Exploitable Results

The Target Users identified for exploitation per KER are outlined in Table 6:

Table 7: Target Users for Exploitation

TG#	Type	Stakeholders concerned	Related KERs
TG1	Primary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine researchers • Data scientists & modellers • Computer scientists • Software developers 	KER 1, 2, 3, 5
TG2	Secondary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMODnet, Copernicus, EDITO • Other EOSC nodes 	KER 3, 4
TG3	Tertiary users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC & international policy bodies • EOSC and national (EOSC related) funding agencies 	KER 6

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10067460>

7 Exploitation measures and resources committed

6.1 Exploitation measures (EM)

Measures towards EO1: Institutional integration in the EOOSC Federation

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
EM1.1	Establish smart federation, interoperability, and two-way interaction between the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) underpinning Blue-Cloud -as operated by D4Science- and EDITO, to enable seamless exploitation of available EDITO resources by EOOSC users via the marine thematic node.	KER 1	TG2	Alignment with the EOOSC Interoperability Framework (EOOSC-IF) achieved
EM1.2	Actively participate in EOOSC governance mechanisms (EOOSC Association) to advocate for the set-up of an EOOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”.	KER 1	TG3	Blue-Cloud 2026 recognized as a candidate node
EM1.3	Find financial resources to support the transition towards an EOOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”	ALL	ALL	Financial resources available to implement the work required to execute transition

Measures towards EO2: Uptake of existing core, generic and thematic services by users working in the marine domain

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
EM2.1	Continue supporting projects currently testing the VRE (i.e., Climarest, FAIR-EASE, SUBMERSE, HIT-RESET Caribbean), to prove sustained value to the research community.	KER 1	TG 1	Synergy projects that continue using VRE for 2 years beyond project end
EM2.2	Offer the Blue-Cloud VRE to new Horizon Europe projects conducting research in the marine and aquatic domains, and support	KER 1	TG 1	New projects that start using the VRE

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
	them in the setup of fit-for-purpose Virtual Labs to support their work (e.g., make the “Marine Omics Observations” VLab that was developed during the FAIR-EASE project by EMBRC fully functional on the Blue-Cloud VRE).			(during/beyond project end)
EM2.3	Promote the Blue-Cloud 2026 Workbenches to Target Audiences following exploitation measures identified in D7.1 Exploitation Plan Workbenches (i.e., publication under CC-BY license in open data repositories e.g., Blue-Cloud Catalogue, Zenodo, Github).	KER 4	TG 1	# of VRE users # of views/downloads of DOIs published, # of citations from DOIs in scientific literature
EM2.4	Foster the ingestion of new integrated datasets stemming from workbenches into EMODnet, CMEMS, SeaDataNet and/or other global repositories, where relevant, for wider dissemination and exploitation by target audiences.	KER 4	TG2	New Blue-Cloud 2026 generated datasets published on relevant marine data services and/or aggregators
EM2.5	Ingest the workbench (pipeline) standards as new methods in the Ocean Best Practice System (OBPS), for wider dissemination and exploitation by target audiences.	KER 4	TG1	# of best practices submitted to OBPS
EM2.6	Promote V Labs and related services to Target Audiences following exploitation measures identified in D7.2 Exploitation Plan Virtual Labs.	KER 4	TG 1	# of VRE users # of views/downloads of DOIs published, # of citations from DOIs in scientific literature
EM2.7	Promote existing set of EO V and EB V pipelines and datasets amongst relevant reporting initiatives (e.g., EU MSFD Technical Groups, CMEMS Ocean State Report, BAMS State of Climate, IPCC) for exploitation of services to deliver monitoring indicators.	KER 4	TG3	# of policy briefs produced feeding from Blue-Cloud 2026 outputs

Measures towards EO3: Uptake of existing (core) services by EOSC nodes, supporting the development of the EOSC Federation

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
EM3.1	Integrate Core and Generic capabilities in the architecture of the EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean”, facilitating direct interactions between components, and providing extensive documentation fit for developers within the EOSC Federation.	KER 2	TG 2	Blue-Cloud VRE integrated as EOSC node
EM3.2	Establish contact with other nodes dealing with related knowledge thematics, such as e.g., in the wider ESFRI environmental domain and support institutes that apply to the EOSC Inter-project grants to expand the services offered through the EOSC Federation and to demonstrate the benefits for end users by onboarding new services into the EOSC Node Digital Twin of the Ocean”.	KER 2	TG 2	# of new services onboarded to EOSC federation via the EOSC Node Digital Twin of the Ocean (receiving cascading grants)

Measures towards EO4: Landscape alignment and added value contribution

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
EM4.1	Onboard existing Workbenches for Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) on EDITO for exploitation of a wider user base, and showcasing the value of data integration for advancing digital twins of the ocean.	KER 4	TG2, TG1	EOV workbenches available on EDITO.
EM4.2	Conduct an assessment of existing EDITO guidelines for onboarding and enrollment of new assets in EDITO versus guidelines and best practices existing for EOSC, reflecting on the gaps/actions required towards alignment.	KER 1, 2, 3, 4	TG 2	Assessment performed by 1Q2027
EM4.3	Identify relevant EOSC assets available in other nodes (e.g., environmental data,	KER 1, 2, 3	TG1	Relevant assets

	socioeconomic data) of potential value for the marine thematic node.			identified by end of 2027
EM4.4	Share key messages of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030 with relevant EC Directorate Generals, to show added value of the KERs to the marine knowledge landscape.	KER 6	TG 3	Relevant messages conveyed to DG RTD, DG MARE, DG DEFIS, DG INPA by end of project

Measures towards EO5: Community Engagement, Capacity Building & Representation

Measure	Description	Related KER	Target User	KPI
EM5.1	Establish collaboration with academic institutions and/or non-academic networks towards offering the Blue-Cloud VRE as a training ground in open science data and tools for scientists, particularly benefiting students in oceanography, marine biology, and related disciplines, as well as those in data analysis and computer sciences.	KER 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	TG 1	#of academic institutions or networks using Blue-Cloud VRE to train early career scientists
EM5.2	Establish collaboration with academic institutions and/or non-academic networks to offer training to early career researchers around (FAIR) data management and topics and use of e-infrastructures.	KER 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	TG 1	#early career researchers trained
EM5.3	Sustain collaboration with OTGA for further exploitation of the training courses developed, towards increasing the user base of KERs.	KER 6	TG 1	#of active courses available in OTGA

6.2 Resources committed towards exploitation

The implementation of the exploitation measures identified in the previous section will require resources to see them through. Some of them will be implemented within the project lifetime, while others will be conditional to the mobilisation of additional resources.

Feeding from the results of an initial exploitation workshop (November 2023), the results of a user survey (March-May 2024) shaped by WP7 partners (SSBE, Trust-IT, CNR-ISTI, MARIS, VLIZ, Ifremer, MOi) and input gathered via 5 targeted interviews carried out by SSBE and VLIZ (March-July 2024), SSBE produced a [Summary of Exploitation Opportunities](#) and hosted 2 additional workshops (Sep 2024 and Nov 2024) to discuss and ground pathways towards exploitation for selected Key Exploitable Results, namely those linked to the Blue-Cloud demonstrators (Virtual Labs and Workbenches). These 2 workshops were organised in close collaboration with all WP7 partners (Trust-IT, CNR-ISTI, MARIS, SSBE, VLIZ, Ifremer, EuroGOOS, EGI, MOi, CMCC, Forth, IRD, OGS, Uliege, INGV, IH, ETHZ), albeit more intensively with WP3 and WP4 Leads (Ifremer, VLIZ), and with participation of WP3 and WP4 partners. The results of these workshops informed the development of the **Individual Exploitation Plans** produced under Task 7.2 (D7.1 and D7.2), and to the further establishment in 2025 of exploitation commitments for the KERs described in this Plan. These commitments will support the exploitation of the project results after the project end date, for a period of 2 years. During that period, these Partners will work together towards mobilising additional resources and successful implementation of the Plan. Existing commitments are listed in the **table** below.

Table 8: Resources Committed Towards Exploitation by Consortium Partners

Related KERs	Commitment	Partner
KER 1, 2	Support normal functioning of existing services during a period of 2 years (2026-2028).	CNR-ISTI
KER 3	Support for normal functioning of existing BDI Beacon deployments during a period of 2 years (2026-2028). Beacon will be regularly updated and upgraded by MARIS and shared via its OpenSource platform. Free and open for all academic usage.	MARIS
KER 3	A two-year basic support and maintenance phase (2026-2028) will ensure the stable, reliable, and productive operation of webODV.	AWI
KER 4	Support exploitation of results beyond the project end (as described in D7.2 Individual VLab Exploitation Plan)	CMCC, CNR, EMBL, ETHZ, FORTH, HCMR, IEEE, Ifremer, IH, INGV, IRD, KNMI, Oceanscope, OGS, Pokapok, SMHI, SOCIB, SU, ULiege, VLIZ
KER 5	Available courses will be active in the OTGA platform for at least 6 months continuously,	IEEE

	then closed for updates, and will be reopened in 2026 for further exploitation until the end of 2026, beyond the project end. The courses will run for an extended period as self-paced courses, as long as its content is considered still relevant and up to date.	
KER 6	Identified Consortium Partners will continue to share key Roadmap messages with Target Audiences through participation in ongoing, relevant initiatives (i.e., EMODnet, CMEMS, EDITO, EOSC, ENVRI-Community) and projects (e.g., others) running from 2026-2028.	SSBE, CNR, Trust-IT, MARIS, Ifremer, VLIZ, MOi, EGI
ALL KERs	Consortium Partners will further progress the implementation of this Exploitation Plan through Call HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01 - EOSC Nodes with federating capabilities for the EOSC Federation, if successful.	CNR, TRUST-IT , COMMPLA, MOI, VLIZ, IFREMER, MARIS, NUBISWARE, EGI, SSBE, IRD, INGV, OGS, FORTH, HCMR, CMCC, ULIEGE, POKAPOK, EMBL, ETHZ, , AWI, IEEE , OCEANSCOPE, EMBRC, CINECA

8 Exploitation targets (2026-2028)

The following Targets will be established to monitor progress towards Exploitation Objectives across the defined Key Performance Indicators (see Table 8):

Table 9: Exploitation Targets Established (2026-2028)

Measure	Related KER	Target User	KPI	Target by 2028
EM1.1	KER 1	TG2	Alignment with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) achieved	Alignment accomplished
EM1.2	KER 1	TG3	Blue-Cloud 2026 recognized as a candidate node	Candidacy accepted

Measure	Related KER	Target User	KPI	Target by 2028
EM1.3	ALL	ALL	Financial resources available to implement the work required to execute transition	Funds secured (>€7.5M)
EM2.1	KER 1	TG 1	Synergy projects that continue using VRE beyond project end	+4 projects (the projects that have signed an MoU and started to explore the VRE are committed to continue working after the end of the project)
EM2.2	KER 1	TG 1	New projects that start using the VRE during project end	+4 projects (Blue-Cloud has signed 4 MoUs with FAIR-EASE, Climarest, SUBMERSE and HIT-RESET Caribbean to build and exploit thematic VREs)
EM2.3	KER 4	TG 1	# of Blue-Cloud VRE users # of views/downloads of DOIs and scientific articles	4,800 users +300 views/downloads
EM2.4	KER 4	TG2	New Blue-Cloud 2026 generated datasets published on relevant marine data services and/or aggregators	+2 EOV datasets published in EMODnet +1 EOV data product in UN Global Oxygen Database
EM2.5	KER 4	TG1	# of best practices submitted to OBPS	2 pipeline (workbench) methods proposed as new method
EM2.6	KER 4	TG 1	# of Blue-Cloud VRE users # of views/downloads of DOIs published	4,800 users +300 views/downloads
EM2.7	KER 1, KER 4		# of policy briefs produced feeding	At least 2 policy briefs

Measure	Related KER	Target User	KPI	Target by 2028
			from Blue-Cloud 2026 outputs	produced (1 EOSC related, 1 marine thematic related)
EM3.1	KER 2	TG 2	Blue-Cloud VRE integrated as EOSC node	Integration achieved
EM3.2	KER 2	TG 2	# of new services onboarded to EOSC federation via the EOSC Node Digital Twin of the Ocean	+3 new services
EM4.1	KER 4	TG2, TG1	EOV workbenches available on EDITO	+3 workbenches
EM4.2	KER 1, 2, 3, 4	TG 2	Assessment performed	Assessment performed by 1Q2027
EM4.3	KER 1, 2, 3	TG1	Relevant assets available in EOSC nodes of interest for marine thematic node	Assessment completed by end of 2027
EM4.4	KER 6	TG 3	Relevant messages conveyed to DG RTD, DG MARE, DG DEFIS, DG INPA by end of project	Inclusion of EOSC Node Digital Twin Ocean in future work programmes and/or EOSC Federation activities.
EM5.1	KER 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	TG 1	#of academic institutions using Blue-Cloud VRE to train early career scientists	+2 (academic institution or non-academic networks)
EM5.2	KER 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	TG 1	#early career researchers trained	+90 participants
EM5.3	KER 6	TG 1	#of active courses available in OTGA and #of enrolled participants	+5 courses +120 participants

9 Intellectual property management

Blue-Cloud 2026 acknowledges the importance of Intellectual Property (IP) and its proper treatment. A project Intellectual Property Policy has been produced at the outset of the project, clarifying the rules, principles and recommendations in regard to the IP aspects that apply to the project results, based on the following main principles:

- Each Blue-Cloud 2026 partner owns the IP of outputs they created.
- The consortium will (non-exclusively) manage and exploit the IP for the benefit of the project.

As for licensing, the Policy will envision that, when permitted by the license terms and conditions applied, IP for relevant items will be licensed under an open-source license.

Ownership of results

Results are owned by the partner that generates them. Joint ownerships apply if:

- A. Specific partners have jointly generated a result and;
- B. It is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.

The joint owners must agree — in writing — on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership ('joint ownership agreement'), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the project Agreement.

Unless otherwise agreed in the joint ownership agreement:

- Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results for non-commercial research on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and
- Each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise exploit the jointly owned results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:
 - at least 45 calendar days advance notice and
 - fair and reasonable compensation.

The joint owners may agree — in writing — to apply another regime than joint ownership.

VRE infrastructure: The Blue-Cloud VRE exploits computational and storage resources, tools and services managed, operated and provisioned by D4Science.org (www.d4science.org). In particular, by exploiting the Analytics Computing Framework and the Storage Manager Framework, it is noted that the ownership of any intellectual property rights is not in any way transferred to D4Science.org. D4Science.org will not be responsible for any issue regulating intellectual property rights infringement or illegal use of user's data, methods, algorithms, workflows, and any other not mentioned digital resources shared through the Blue-Cloud VRE. All the improvements, enhancements and modifications to the common services enabling the Blue-Cloud VRE will be released as components of the gCube framework (<https://www.gcube-system.org/>) licensed with the European Union Public Licence EUPL v1.1 open-source licence.

WorkBenches: Datasets obtained thanks to the WorkBenches will be CC-BY 4.0 (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). WorkBenches (workflow, notebook) will be open-source licenses (e.g., GPL, MIT) and transferable to any other big data infrastructure. It is explicitly noted that ownership of any IP rights for user-contributed resources (data, methods, algorithms, workflows) is not transferred to D4Science, EDITO Datalab, nor their operational bodies. All improvements to the common services enabling the EOSC Node will be released as components of the underlying open-source framework, also licensed under the EUPL or Apache 2.0.

10 Conclusion

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has developed a digital ecosystem that offers researchers a combination of analytical services and tools, coupled with computing resources, which enables them to improve the transformation of marine data to products, progress more efficient modelling of ocean variables, support environmental analytical data services, inspire and accelerate community-driven innovation and collaborate at a European and global scale. Its integration in EOSC as a marine thematic node will enable its exploitation by a wider and more diverse user base, and contribute to support key European assets (EMODnet, Copernicus Marine Service, EDITO) in driving data provision into EOSC. It will also contribute to foster cross-discipline research in support of greater social objectives, such as those addressed by the EU Mission “Protect our Ocean and Waters” and the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development.

This Joint Exploitation Plan establishes the objectives, measures, and commitments undertaken by Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium Partners to pursue such an exploitation strategy, and the targets set forth towards this end.

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